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Optimizing 3D Container Loading in Maritime Logistics: Classical A3C vs Quantum-Augmented QA3C

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ABSTRACT

Efficient container placement in maritime logistics poses a high-dimensional, constraint-driven optimization problem where classical reinforcement learning approaches often struggle to maintain spatial consistency under irregular and dynamic input conditions. This study introduces and evaluates a quantum-augmented reinforcement learning model (QA3C), which integrates low-qubit parametric quantum circuits into the classical asynchronous advantage actor-critic (A3C) framework, offering a novel approach to enhancing spatial decision quality in constrained 3D loading tasks. Both models were trained and tested using synthetic scenarios involving 300, 350, and 400 boxes across four qubit configurations (0, 5, 10, and 15), with each setup evaluated over fifty trials. QA3C improved fill rate by up to 9.56 points relative to the classical baseline (0 qubit) and produced more regular, layered placements. While its training time ranged from 47 to 153 seconds, depending on circuit depth, decision steps remained computationally manageable. Although QA3C delivered more consistent performance and structural compactness, the highest observed fill rate (72.39%) was achieved in the 400-box scenario with 10 qubits. These findings demonstrate that quantum-enhanced reinforcement learning can overcome convergence limitations in classical models, contributing to more efficient space utilization in semi-real-time container logistics planning.

1 INTRODUCTION

Container loading is a complex combinatorial optimization problem that involves arranging multiple boxes within a limited three-dimensional space while adhering to constraints such as stacking order, accessibility, and minimizing unused volume [1]. With the increasing global trade and digitalization in maritime logistics, there is a growing interest in utilizing intelligent systems to enhance cargo placement strategies, particularly in standard 20-foot containers used for international transport.

While conventional optimization methods offer deterministic solutions, they often fail to adapt under dynamic or irregular input conditions [30]. Traditional rule-based or optimization-driven methods frequently fall short in dynamic scenarios due to the exponential growth of the solution space as the number of boxes increases. Reinforcement learning (RL) offers a promising alternative by

enabling agents to adapt through interaction. Classical A3C, while effective in simpler scenarios, often fails to maintain spatial consistency and fill efficiency when dealing with irregular box sequences and complex stacking constraints [2]. Recent studies have shown that classical heuristics, including greedy, shelf-based, and metaheuristic algorithms, encounter scalability issues in complex three-dimensional bin packing problems, especially when item sequences are dynamic or operational constraints are present [29, 30]. Although approaches such as First-Fit and Tabu Search can be effective in static settings, their performance often deteriorates when faced with real-world requirements, including stacking rules, loading order, or varying box attributes [31, 32]. These limitations have led to growing interest in learning-based frameworks that better accommodate the complexity and variability of realistic packing tasks.

One promising direction is the integration of quantum computing into reinforcement learning. This combination has led to quantum reinforcement learning (QRL), where classical optimization is combined with quantum-enhanced exploration to evaluate multiple policies simultaneously through superposition. This study implements a quantum-augmented actor-critic model named QA3C, where Parametric Quantum Circuits (PQC) encode input features into quantum states. This design enables broader and more efficient policy search, leading to more compact and consistent container loading patterns [3]. Beyond its theoretical appeal, quantum-enhanced RL has practical implications for maritime logistics, where time-sensitive and spatially constrained operations require fast, adaptive decision-making. Recent AI-based applications in Brazilian, Dutch, and American ports have demonstrated that predictive analytics and digital twin models can reduce turnaround time, enhance equipment utilization, and improve safety [4–6]. These developments demonstrate the feasibility of intelligent control systems in real-world seaport operations.

This study aims to evaluate whether a quantum-augmented actor-critic model can improve spatial consistency, fill efficiency, and learning behavior in constrained 3D container loading scenarios. Both the classical A3C and the quantum-enhanced QA3C models are tested in identical simulation environments, and their performance is compared across key metrics, including fill rate, stacking regularity, training time, and placement accuracy. The main contribution of this study lies in demonstrating that low-qubit quantum circuits, when embedded into reinforcement learning architectures, can generate more compact and consistent placement outcomes, particularly under mid-scale, irregular, and resource-constrained conditions. Such improvements are especially relevant in real-time or semi-automated logistics planning tasks, where decisions must strike a balance between speed, accuracy, and spatial optimization.

2 RELATED WORK

As digital technologies continue to integrate into logistics and maritime operations, artificial intelligence and quantum computing have become increasingly relevant for complex planning tasks. Among the methods explored, reinforcement learning (RL) and quantum reinforcement learning (QRL) have attracted attention due to their potential to handle dynamic and high-dimensional decision problems. Container loading, which often involves spatial constraints and sequential placement decisions, has been identified as one area where these approaches could offer meaningful improvements over classical optimization techniques. Phillipson [3] conceptually examined how hybrid quantum-classical methods can improve decision accuracy and computational speed in logistics applications, including cargo loading. Nagy et al. [7] supported this idea by demonstrating that hybrid QRL models perform better in uncertain environments. In contrast, Tomar et al. [8] proposed a QRL-based routing framework that yielded more stable results under real-time conditions.

Beyond conceptual frameworks, several studies have applied QRL to concrete optimization problems. Romero et al. [4] and Correll et al. [9] used quantum neural networks and variational circuits to optimize layout tasks such as container stacking and bin packing. Studies in ports such as Rotterdam and Corpus Christi, as well as predictive modeling at Brazilian terminals, have also shown that AI-based systems can automate operational planning in smart port environments [5, 6]. In

parallel, another group of studies focused on improving the internal architecture of QRL agents. Andrés et al. [10] aimed to reduce computational costs by designing dimension reduction strategies, while Chen and Yu [11] explored the use of quantum-inspired recurrent models for improved control. Lamata [2] contributed basic QRL protocols for superconducting systems, and Reuer et al. [12] tested deep RL agents under real-time feedback in quantum settings.

Skolik et al. [13] tested variational QRL agents in classical simulation environments, while Zoufal et al. [14] applied quantum GANs to improve the learning of probability distributions. Willsch et al. [15] demonstrated how QAOA can be applied in combinatorial settings. Rudin et al. [16] also emphasized that explainability remains crucial in AI-supported logistics, particularly in systems where transparency is required. Within the maritime domain, reinforcement learning techniques have also been applied to various operational challenges. Abdalla et al. [17] used deep RL for emission control in hybrid ship power systems, while Dutta et al. [18] applied RL to container network design. Alqithami [19] proposed a hierarchical RL model for multi-agent sustainable transport, and Wakita [20] used model-based RL to support autonomous ship navigation.

While previous studies have explored quantum-enhanced reinforcement learning in theoretical or simplified logistics settings, empirical evaluations in constrained 3D environments remain limited. In contrast to prior work, this study implements and benchmarks a low-qubit QA3C model using realistic container loading scenarios with non-trivial box configurations, dynamic item sequences, and practical spatial constraints. The focus is on understanding how hybrid quantum-classical agents behave under these conditions and whether they can improve placement consistency and overall loading efficiency.

3 METHODOLOGY

Container placement is modeled as a sequential decision-making problem in a large and complex spatial environment. For this reason, reinforcement learning (RL) methods are employed to optimize the arrangement of boxes within a 20 ft container. The study compares two types of solutions: classical RL models and quantum-enhanced versions.

Figure 1: Conceptual architecture of classical and quantum RL-based container placement

Figure 1 illustrates the primary concept underlying this comparison. The environment consists of three box sizes (small, medium, and large), each of which must be efficiently placed within the container. Classical RL models try to learn this behavior using only experience and feedback. On the other hand, quantum models include additional layers made of quantum circuits. These circuits enhance the model's ability to explore various combinations and improve decision quality. The training process aims to minimize unused container volume while complying with regulations regarding stability and accessibility. The model sees a random box in each episode and decides where to place it. The primary performance metric is the fill rate, but other aspects such as layout regularity and training speed are also considered. The remainder of this section presents the RL structure, the quantum circuit integration, the experimental setup, and the dataset design.

3.1 Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement learning is a method where an agent learns to make decisions by interacting with its environment and receiving feedback in the form of rewards. This process is typically formulated as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), consisting of a set of states S , a set of actions A , a reward function $R(s, a)$, and a transition probability function $P(s'|s, a)$ [21]. The learning objective is to find a policy that maximizes the expected return, as expressed by the Bellman Optimality Equation (1) [22]:

$$V(s) = \max_a [R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s'} P(s'|s, a) V(s')] \quad (1)$$

In this expression, γ is the discount factor that determines the weight of future rewards. $R(s, a)$ represents the immediate reward after taking action a in state s , and $P(s'|s, a)$ is the probability of transitioning to the state s' from s after action a .

Reinforcement learning techniques can be classified into two categories: model-based and model-free. Model-based methods attempt to learn or utilize the functions P and R to simulate outcomes, whereas model-free methods learn policies directly from experience without relying on explicit environment models [23]. This study adopts a model-free strategy, as constructing a reliable container packing model would require unrealistic assumptions about item shapes, sequences, and spatial transitions. Learning directly from simulated episodes allows agents to optimize placement behavior without estimating P or R .

The algorithm used here is Asynchronous Advantage Actor-Critic (A3C), which runs several agents in parallel and updates policy and value networks independently [24]. Its quantum-enhanced version, called QA3C, extends the policy network with a small, parametrized quantum circuit designed using PennyLane, aiming to explore whether such hybrid integration can improve placement efficiency [25].

3.2 Quantum-Enhanced Learning

Quantum-enhanced reinforcement learning systems are hybrid models that extend classical RL structures with quantum circuits to enhance their representational capacity. In this study, quantum modeling is performed using Parametric Quantum Circuits (PQCs). These circuits project classical inputs into a high-dimensional Hilbert space, allowing more expressive feature representations and helping to overcome the limited non-linearity of classical models [26]. The circuits are implemented with the PennyLane library and structured as three-layer variational quantum circuits (VQC), which operate in parallel with the classical policy network. Each qubit is rotated using a parametrized angle calculated from the input vector. The composite rotation gate used in the quantum transformation is defined in Equation (2) [25]:

$$Rot(\theta, \phi, \lambda) = RZ(\phi) \cdot RY(\theta) \cdot RZ(\lambda) \quad (2)$$

In this notation, RZ and RY denote quantum rotation gates around the Z and Y axes, respectively, while θ , ϕ , and λ are trainable rotation parameters derived from classical input features. This multi-axis rotation enables the circuit to encode richer feature interactions, which classical linear layers may fail to represent, especially in limited-depth policy networks. In this way, the classical policy network is enhanced through quantum features and increased flexibility in function approximation.

Preliminary experiments showed that the 10-qubit configuration achieved more stable convergence and higher fill rates than the 15-qubit version. Although deeper circuits can, in theory, offer greater expressive capacity, this outcome aligns with known challenges in optimizing variational quantum circuits. Increasing circuit depth is associated with barren plateau effects, where gradients

vanish and training becomes ineffective as the parameter space grows [33]. Since the input features in this task are relatively low-dimensional, additional qubit layers did not improve learning and, in some cases, introduced instability. Therefore, the PQC architecture was selected based on empirical performance across multiple depths and was designed to balance expressibility and trainability in spatial decision-making for packing tasks [26].

3.3 Experimental Setup

The experimental setup aims to compare the classical A3C algorithm and its quantum-enhanced counterpart, QA3C, in a 20-foot container box-loading task. In each episode, the agent places small, medium, and large boxes that appear at random positions inside the container. The overall workflow consists of four structured stages, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Four-stage experimental workflow for container placement optimization

As illustrated in Figure 2, the experiment follows a structured four-stage workflow.

The first stage defines the simulation environment by setting parameters such as container volume, box sizes, destination-city information, and spatial gap constraints. Each box is labeled according to its delivery city, following an unloading priority from east to west. Model selection and training are carried out in the second stage: the classical A3C algorithm is used as a baseline, while QA3C is formed by extending A3C with low-qubit Parametric Quantum Circuits (PQC). Quantum circuits with 5 and 10 qubits are configured and integrated into the policy network. In the third stage, PQC outputs are directly linked to the classical policy network, guiding action selection. The training is performed using the default qubit simulator available in the PennyLane library [34]. The final stage involves evaluating model performance using several metrics, including fill (occupancy) rate, skip (unplaced) rate, total training time, and decision-making latency. In addition to numerical outputs, visual comparisons are used to assess stacking regularity and space utilization within the container.

Although a standard 20-foot container can accommodate over 1000 small boxes under tight configurations, this study limits test cases to 300, 350, and 400 boxes. The reduction is intentional to ensure convergence and comparability across model variants within a feasible training duration. Larger-scale simulations are planned as part of future work involving performance benchmarking under more demanding conditions.

3.4 Dataset Description and Container Capacity Estimation

The dataset used in this study was designed to simulate realistic conditions for container loading. It includes synthetic box data generated using key attributes such as size, weight, and

destination. To improve operational handling, boxes planned for longer routes were placed toward the rear of the container, supporting more efficient unloading during intermediate stops. A synthetic dataset was created using box size, route, and weight variables, while additional tests were conducted on verified layouts from a real container plan. In the quantum-enhanced setup, the number of qubits was first varied while the number of boxes was kept constant, and then the opposite was done to see how the model responded to increased load.

Basic volume calculations were performed on a standard 20-foot container to estimate the container's usable capacity. Three box sizes were considered, resulting in approximate capacities of 1,229 small boxes, 346 medium boxes, and 115 large boxes. The average of these values, 563.33, was used as a reference to create test scenarios with varying box quantities. These scenarios were used to evaluate both the classical and quantum-enhanced versions of the A3C algorithm, and their performance was assessed using several key indicators, including qubit count, number of placed and unplaced boxes, success rate, skip rate, fill rate, training time, and decision step count.

3.5 Limitations

The current simulation environment focuses solely on geometric packing and does not incorporate operational constraints such as weight distribution, stacking stability, item fragility, or loading/unloading sequences. These simplifications were made intentionally to isolate the effects of spatial policy learning. However, these real-world factors are critical in practical container operations. A follow-up version of the environment is being developed to support weight-sensitive reward shaping and stacking order constraints based on delivery priorities. This extension is intended to facilitate more realistic evaluations under practical logistics conditions. Incorporating such operational constraints will help assess the robustness and generalizability of the QA3C model in real-world container loading scenarios.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental results compare the classical A3C model with its quantum-augmented variant, QA3C, across a range of container placement tasks. The analysis focuses on fill rate, placement success, and training time, complemented by structural evaluations and visual outputs under varying qubit and box configurations.

4.1 Performance Analysis of the QA3C Model

The QA3C model was tested under various qubit configurations and box quantities to observe how quantum depth affects placement efficiency. Table 1 presents key metrics, including fill rate, skip rate, and training time across different configurations.

Table 1: Performance results of the QA3C model under different box quantities

Boxes	Qubits	Success Rate	Placed	Unplaced	Skip Rate	Fill Rate	Training Time (s)	Steps
400	0	61.75%	247	153	38.25%	62.83%	1.46	342
400	5	60.50%	242	158	39.50%	70.14%	12.30	342
400	10	61.25%	245	155	38.75%	72.39%	16.31	342
400	15	61.25%	245	155	38.75%	70.37%	21.46	342
350	0	64.57%	226	124	35.43%	63.79%	1.40	298
350	5	65.14%	228	122	34.86%	68.11%	10.70	298
350	10	64.57%	226	124	35.43%	71.04%	11.54	298
350	15	64.00%	224	126	36.00%	71.96%	15.00	298
300	0	63.33%	190	110	36.67%	64.59%	9.00	265
300	5	63.00%	189	111	37.00%	68.20%	6.60	265
300	10	65.00%	195	105	35.00%	63.48%	7.40	265
300	15	65.67%	197	103	34.33%	66.48%	10.60	265

As the number of qubits increased, the model generally produced more structured and clustered layouts, particularly under low to medium box densities. The success rate represents the proportion of boxes successfully placed inside the container and is included to complement the fill rate when evaluating spatial efficiency.

The results show that the QA3C model benefits from quantum integration, especially under low to medium box densities, improving fill rates and spatial stacking consistency. Beyond 10 qubits, training time exhibits a modest increase, although the magnitude of change varies depending on the box count. The highest fill rate (72.39%) was observed in the 400-box scenario with ten qubits. While the classical model achieved the highest single fill rate in a specific scenario, QA3C consistently produced more structured placements and competitive fill rates across varying configurations.

4.2 Visual Placement Analysis of the QA3C Model

Visualization facilitates a deeper understanding of the QA3C model's behavior beyond what numerical indicators alone can convey. When the number of boxes is fixed and the number of qubits is varied (0, 5, 10, 15), the spatial arrangements reveal how quantum depth influences placement compactness, stacking order, and container space usage. Figure 3 presents the spatial configurations produced by the QA3C model under four qubit settings, with the number of boxes fixed at 300.

Figure 3: Container placement outcomes for QA3C with 300 boxes under different qubit counts

As the quantum depth increases, placements shift from irregular and fragmented to more stratified and compact forms. At 0 qubits (64.59% fill, 63.33% success), the layout is loose, with high void ratios and minimal structure. This outcome reflects the classical A3C's limited spatial awareness. At 5 qubits (68.20% fill, 63.00% success), placements become more compact, gaps begin to shrink, and early signs of vertical segmentation appear, suggesting that the QA3C model is starting to internalize spatial constraints. This trend continues with 10 qubits (63.48% fill, 65.00% success), where stack patterns grow more consistent and balanced, despite a slight decrease in fill rate. The improvement in structure, along with a reduction in training time, hints at more efficient learning dynamics. At 15 qubits (66.48% fill, 65.67% success), the model forms dense, symmetrical stacks across both axes. Although further improvements plateau beyond this point, the emergence of clean, layered placements suggests that QA3C can generalize more effectively and maintain structural order even under randomized inputs.

A second visual comparison was conducted by fixing the qubit count at 10 and increasing the number of boxes (300, 350, 400) to observe how the model adapts under higher volume conditions. This setting enables the assessment of the QA3C model's scalability when spatial constraints become tighter and placement options increase combinatorially. In particular, the aim is to evaluate whether the learned stacking behavior remains stable as the container approaches full capacity. Figure 4 presents the visual configurations for these scenarios.

Figure 4: QA3C placement patterns with fixed qubit count (10) and increasing box numbers

As the number of boxes increases from 300 to 400 under a fixed 10-qubit configuration, the QA3C model exhibits progressively more organized and compact stacking behavior. In the 300-box scenario (63.48% fill, 65.00% success), placements remain partially irregular, with visible gaps especially in the upper layers. The lower levels are anchored by large boxes, but the model has yet to achieve a consistent layered structure. When the box count reaches 350 (71.04% fill, 64.57% success), horizontal alignment improves, and segmentation patterns become more evident, reducing spatial inefficiencies. At 400 boxes (72.39% fill, 61.25% success), the container is nearly saturated, exhibiting well-structured layers with minimal voids; however, the success rate slightly decreases due to increased placement complexity.

These results suggest that QA3C maintains structural consistency even as input size increases. The emergence of layered formations and reduced fragmentation at higher densities highlight the model's capacity to scale under constraint. Despite a growing number of possible placement permutations, the model continues to preserve its stacking regularity and segmentation clarity, indicating robustness against input complexity. In contrast to classical A3C, QA3C consistently produces more regular, compact, and stratified placements, making it a strong candidate for high-volume, real-time container loading tasks where both efficiency and order are essential.

4.3 Comparative Evaluation and Discussion

This study addressed the container placement problem by comparing the classical A3C reinforcement learning algorithm with its quantum-augmented counterpart, QA3C. By integrating low-qubit parametric quantum circuits into the policy network, the QA3C model generated more compact and regular stacking patterns across various loading scenarios. These outcomes align with prior research suggesting that hybrid quantum-classical models can enhance spatial organization and policy robustness in constrained environments [1, 7, 8]. Compared to classical agents, QA3C demonstrated greater consistency under dense and irregular configurations, suggesting improved generalization in spatial decision-making.

Although classical reinforcement learning techniques have shown success in logistics-related tasks such as routing and container optimization [4, 5], their performance often deteriorates in high-dimensional or dynamically changing environments [1, 9]. Recent findings suggest that quantum-enhanced reinforcement learning can alleviate these limitations by enhancing convergence speed and enabling the learning of more expressive policies with fewer samples [10]. Specifically, incorporating quantum circuits into actor-critic architectures has been associated with improved structural stability and better geometric efficiency in packing tasks [1, 12]. Nonetheless, several barriers remain for the practical deployment of quantum-enhanced agents. Hardware-level challenges such as qubit decoherence, gate noise, and circuit depth limitations may hinder reproducibility in real-world conditions [2, 15]. While policy stability improvements have also been reported in quantum control settings [27], the interpretability of QRL-based decisions remains an open concern, particularly in safety-critical applications such as cargo planning and real-time logistics [16].

The QA3C model yielded denser and more structured layouts, especially at moderate box volumes and under optimal quantum configurations (e.g., 5–10 qubits). These findings point to the potential of quantum-enhanced models for real-time or near-real-time logistics planning in spatially constrained environments. Previous work has shown that quantum-inspired methods can reduce sample complexity while maintaining control efficiency [28], which could be beneficial in low-resource operational platforms.

5 CONCLUSION

This paper examined 3D container loading using a classical reinforcement learning model (A3C) and its quantum-augmented variant (QA3C), where parametric quantum circuits were embedded into the policy network. Experimental results showed that QA3C achieved higher fill rates and more regular stacking structures across various loading scenarios. The model was particularly effective under moderate qubit configurations, generating compact, layered arrangements that reduced unused volume. These findings support the view that even low-qubit quantum reinforcement learning can enhance spatial decision-making in constrained environments. While the classical agent performed adequately, QA3C delivered improvements in geometric consistency and packing efficiency without introducing excessive training time, except under high-density scenarios where gains plateau and success rates begin to decline.

Future work may explore extending this hybrid architecture to more complex logistics problems with dynamic inputs, route dependencies, or real-time constraints. Evaluating QA3C using operational data, which includes box fragility, weight distribution, and unloading priorities, could clarify its practical relevance. Comparative studies of model-free and model-based QRL approaches may further illuminate their respective strengths. For deployment, concerns around transparency, decision interpretability, and computational feasibility must be addressed, especially in autonomous systems or embedded digital twin platforms.

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